
AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
ONLINE LOCKER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
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1. INTRODUCTION

Online Locker Management System” is a comprehensive tool designed to cater all the needs of bank lockers; be it signing up new customers, maintaining billing records, checking the locker traffic of any customer or extracting employees’ attendance. LMIS is one window solution for any bank to tackle all the bank locker issues and thrive in the business by being most organized and effective. There are two sorts of customers in a bank locker – one existing bank customers and second non-customers. The information gathering for both these type of customers varies as bank already have most of the information about its existing customers while it needs everything from scratch for non-customers. Thus, registration forms are different and so is the data entry process – OLMS will import all the necessary details from dedicated database for existing bank customers and create new files for new customers.

Besides sign up process, there are other details that can be maintained and recorded like traffic record, locker location, insurance details, monthly fee, initial deposit, locker expiry date etc.

Bank lockers need a proper and accurate system for recording right time of customers and employees’ check-in and check-out. This data can be recorded manually – the customers get in and the front desk officer asks him/her to mark the attendance along with time and signature. Well it is time consuming, it irritates the customer and also, there is a fair chance of human error.

An ideal way to allow the traffic inside the locker will be via thumb impression or any other identification verification procedure. LMIS records the check-in and check-out time of the customers and employees exactly in the same manner, which provides enhanced security and an effective and accurate method of recording very crucial information.

Report generation is the key to assess performance of any department in any bank. In a bank locker, some reports are obvious and compulsory; LMIS has a built-in report generation system for such reports like employees check-in time. But too many other reports are varied and different, for instance if the bank wants to see all the customers who have

visited on Thursdays in any particular month, LMIS allows advanced search filters and one can generate report for the same. The dynamic factor is not customized report generation but any report can be emailed to anybody in the bank or even outside via Online Locker Management System. Emails serve as a reminder in the bank lockers world. The bank requires to send plenty of emails to its customers like sending monthly invoices, reminding about the last payment date, sending details of customers' visit, welcome mail on sign up, birthday wishes and plenty of related stuff. OLMS has abundance of email templates for different purposes, the bank can add even more templates as per its policies and functions in the software.

Moving on from emails to customers, bank locker department has monthly reports to be sent via email to various other departments in the bank. OLMS allows bank locker to automate this process or one can perform this task manually depending upon the convenience and nature of reports.

1.1. Project Overview

The Online Locker Management System is developed as a web application using PHP. The Online Locker Management System is a complete web portal where all information regarding all required information of locker can be easily available by customers. This site enables you to get quick and updated information.

1 Design of Modules

Design is the first step in the development phase for many engineered products or systems. It may be defined as the process of applying various techniques and principles for the purpose of defining a device, a process or a system in sufficient detail to permit its physical realization. The purpose of the design phase is to plan a solution of the program

specified by the required document. In other words, starting with what is needed: take us towards how to satisfy needs. Computer software design like engineering design approaches in other disciplines changes continually as new methods, better analysis and broader understanding evolve.

1 **Characteristics of Design**

A design should exhibit a hierarchical organization that makes intelligent use of control among components of the software. A design should be modular that is, the software should be logical. A design should contain distinct and separable representation of data and procedure. A design should lead to modules. A design should lead to interface that reduce the complexity of the connections between modules and with the external environment.

Using one of a number of design methods the design step produces a data design, an architectural design and a procedural design. Preliminary design is concerned with transformation requirements to data and software architectures. Detailed design focus on refinements to architectural representation that lead to detailed data structure and algorithmic representation for software.

The data design transforms the information domain model created during analysis into the data structures that will be required to

implement the software. The architectural design defines a relationship among major structural components into a procedural description of the software.

2 Modules in the system

The different modules that will make the whole system are as follows:

Module Description

Records Of Customer's Account

- Account No.
- Associated Locker
- Locker description
- New User Registration

Admin Login

Customer Login

2. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 System Analysis

System analysis is the process of identification of the objectives and requirements, evaluation of alternative solutions and recommendation for a more feasible solution. In other words, system analysis is the step-by-step process of gathering, recording and interpreting facts. It is the reduction of an entire system by studying the various operations. It includes studying the problems encountered in the present system and introducing a new computer system into an organization. The main aim of analysis is to determine problem areas and decide on solutions to reduce or eliminate them. System analysis is a detailed study of the various operations performed by a system and the relationship within outside of the system. System analysis helps to understand the problem and emphasizes what is needed from the system. The various user requirements are identified and a new system is proposed so as to meet those requirements.

System analysis is an approach to the study and solution of problem using computer based system; it provides a framework for visualizing the organizational facts that operates on the system. The aspect of analysis is defining the boundaries of the system and determining whether or not a candidate system should consider other related system.

During analysis the data are collected from available documents, decision points and transaction handle by the present system.

System analysis itself breaks into two stages. Preliminary and Detailed. During preliminary analysis the analyst list the objectives of the proposed system. These findings come together in the preliminary report.

Once the preliminary report is approved, the system analysis phase advances into a second stage. During detailed analysis required data and information are collected and a detailed study is made. During analysis, data are collected on the available files, decision points, and transactions of the system using various tools like data flow diagram.

2.2Proposed System

It is a complete web portal where information regarding the Customer Locker information searched online.

➤ Initial investigation

The facts finding techniques in this project employed are data collection, Websites and book references.

3.FEASIBILITY STUDY

In any project, feasibility analysis is a very important stage. Feasibility study is system proposal according to its workability, impact on the operation, ability to meet user needs and efficient use of resources. Any project may face scarcity in resources, time or workforce. An important outcome of the preliminary investigation is the determination whether the system requested is feasible or not. The key considerations involved in the feasibility analysis are technical, operational, and economic.

3.1 Technical feasibility

Technical feasibility is the most important of all types of feasibility analysis. Technical feasibility deals with hardware as well as software requirements. An idea from the outline design to system requirements in terms of inputs outputs, files and procedures is drawn and the type of hardware, software, and the methods required for running the systems are analyzed. Keeping in mind of the above considerations, the resource availability at this company was observed.

In this project it was found that the company has the sufficient resources to develop the project. Software requirements are PHP,MYSQL,HTML,CSS,JAVASCRIPT.That is also available. Hence the project is technically feasible for development in this company.

3.2 Economic feasibility

Economic analysis is the most frequently used method for evaluating the effectiveness of the software, more commonly known as the cost /benefit analysis. The procedure is to determine the benefits and savings that are expected from a candidate system and compare them with costs. If the benefits outweigh cost, the decision is made to design and implement the system; otherwise further alternatives have to be made. Here it is seen that no new hardware or software is needed for the development of the system. There for the cost for developing the system is less than the benefit. Hence the project is economically feasible for development in this company.

3.3 Behavioral feasibility

An estimate should be made of how strong a reaction the user staff is likely to have toward the development of a computerized system. It is common knowledge the computer installations have something to do understandable that the introduction of a candidate system requires special effort to educate, sell and train the staff on new ways of considering business. I have tried this project under several conditions with many different users.

3.4 Operational feasibility

The purpose of the operational feasibility study is to determine

whether the new system would be used if it is developed and implemented? Will there be resistance from users that will undermine the possible application benefits? From the outputs of the meeting that was held with the system users, it was found that all of them support the development of new system. The positive response from them encouraged in building such a system.

4. SOFTWARE ENGINEERING PARADIGM

4.1 Waterfall model

The simplest, oldest and most widely used process model for software designing is the waterfall model. It was proposed by Royce in 1970. The essence of this software paradigm is that the process of software designing consists of linear set of distinct phases.

These phases are:

1 Stage1: Feasibility Study

The goal of feasibility study is to evaluate alternative systems and to purpose the most feasible and desirable system for designing. Five types of feasibility are addressed in this study.

1. Technical feasibility
2. Economic Feasibility
3. Motivational Feasibility
4. Schedule Feasibility
5. Operational Feasibility

2 Stage2: Requirement Analysis and Specification

The goal of this phase is to understand the exact requirements of the users and to document them properly. This activity is usually executed together with the users, as the goal is to document all functions, performance and interfacing requirements for the software designing and management. The requirements describe “what” of a system. This phase

produces a large document containing a description of what the system will do without describing how it will be done. This document is known as software requirement specification (SRS) document.

3 Stage3: Design

The goal of this phase is to transform the requirement specification produced in the requirement analysis phase into a structure that is suitable for implementation in some programming language, Here, overall software architecture is defined, and the product design and detailed design work is performed. This work is documented and is known as software design description (SDD document).

4 Stage4: Coding and Unit Testing

The information contained in SPMS is sufficient to begin the coding Phase. The coding Phase of software designing involves translation of design specification into a machine readable form. If design is performed in a detailed manner, code generation can be accomplished easily. This phase is also known as the implementation phase. Here, each component of the design is implemented as a program module, and each of these program modules is unit tested. The purpose of unit testing is to determine the correct working of individual modules.

5 Stage5: Integration and System Testing:

During this phase the different program modules are integrated in a planned way and then tested as a completed system to ensure that the designed system functions according to its requirements as

specified in the SRS document.

Stage6: Software Maintenance

This is the last phase of software designing which includes a broad set of activities such as error correction, enhancement of capabilities, deletion of obsolete capabilities and optimization.

We have followed the above defined model for the development of our project. The above model “The Waterfall Model”, works on the basis of SDLC which I have learned in the first year of our MCA curriculum and I have applied it in my project titled Online Locker Management System.

Advantages

1. Simple and easy to use.
2. Easily manageable.
3. The phase of the model are processed and completed one at a time.
4. Works very well for smaller software projects.

Disadvantages

1. It is often difficult for the user to state all the requirements explicitly.
2. Real projects rarely follow the sequential flow that the software model proposes.

5. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

A main purpose of software requirement specification is the clear definition and specification of functionality and of the software product. It allows the developer to be carried out, performance level to be obtained and corresponding interface to be established. This section list out the requirement for developing a software project monitoring system

5.1. Hardware requirements

The following are the hardware constraints:

Processor	:	Core i3 or Above.
Main Memory	:	2GB RAM.
CPU speed	:	800MHZ.
Hard Disk capacity	:	500GB or Above.

5.2. Software requirements

Operating system	:	Windows8 pro
Web server	:	APACHE
Frontend	:	PHP
Backend	:	MySQL
Browser	:	Internet Explorer

5.3 Overview of Software

In the project Software project monitoring system PHP Framework is used as front-end tool. PHP is used in this project.

An interface for users is build-using PHP.MY SQL Server is used as the back-end tool.

Introduction To PHP

PHP stands for Hypertext processors, is probably the most popular scripting language on the web. It is used to enhance web pages. With PHP, you can do things like create username and password login pages, check details from, create forms, picture galleries, surveys and a whole lot more. If you come across a web page that ends in PHP, then the author has written the some programming code to liven up the plain, old HTML.

PHP is also known as server side scripting language. That is because the PHP doesn't get executed on your computer, but on the computer you request the page from. The request are then handed by you, and displayed in your browser. PHP code are interpreted by a web server with a PHP processor module, which generates the resulting web page. PHP command can be embedded directly into an HTML source document other than calling a n external file to process data. It has also involved to include to

include a command-line interface capability and can be used in stand alone graphical applications.

PHP code is placed in the body of HTML code. It may be placed in HTML code as follows:

```
<PHP  
echo "This is a test of PHP!";  
?>
```

The above example will output the quoted text on the HTML page where the PHP code is embedded.

PHP is a free software released under the PHP license ,which is in comparatively with the GNU general public license (GPL) due to restriction on the usage of the term PHP.PHP can be developed on each web servers and also as a standalone shell on almost every operating system and platform, free of charge .We preferred PHP for this web page because of the following reasons:

- **Simple and easy to learn:** PHP scripting is definitely one of the easiest, if not the easiest scripting language to learn and grasp for developers.This is partially due to the similarities PHP has with C and Java.Even if the only knowledge of development that you have is with HTML,picking up PHp is still fairly easy. For developers just starting out ,PHP is often the first scripting language they learn because it's clear and easy to understand.

- **Supports:**The last thing you want as a developer is to be “stuck” with a coding issue and not have anywhere to go for help or answers. Since PHP is so popular and widely used , finding help or documentation for PHP online is extremely easy. The best part is the support is free through forums, PDFs ,blogs ,and social media.The facts that it’s open source also contributes to the large support community of PHP and LAMP(Linux, apache,Mysql and PHP) in general .PHP has the largest user base of any scripting language .
- **Free:** There are no cost associated with using PHP, including updates. Keeping costs down is a goal of business and developer as well. So the fact that you can code programs with PHP for free is huge benefit that you won't get with JSP,ASP,or other scripting languages that requires paid hosting .There are no licenses, restrictions, royalty fees involved at all .PHP is 100% free for anyone to use.
- **Earlier to fix problems:** When it comes to the web application development ,you are bound to run into issues and come across the occasional “fail” .But the benefit you get with PHP is the problems aren't as difficult to find and fix as they are with every languages . This is because with each request ,PHP cleans up and starts over .So an issue with one request will not necessarily disrupt another.

- **Object Oriented:** PHP actually has the ability to call Java and Windows COM objects. In addition to this ,you can create custom classes. Other classes can actually borrow from those custom classes as well which extends the capabilities of PHP even further.
- **Speed:** Since PHP does not use a lot of a system's resources in order to run, it operates much faster than other scripting languages. Hosting PHP is also very easy and lot of hosts provides support for PHP. Even when used with other software, PHP still retains speed without slowing down other processes. Being that PHP is a mature language, it is also fairly stable because all the kinks have been worked over years.

Using remote files

XAMPP :It is a free and open source cross-platform web server solution stack package developed by Apache Friends, consisting mainly of the Apache HTTP Server, MySQL database, and interpreters for scripts written in the PHP and Perl programming languages.

XAMPP is regularly updated to incorporate the latest releases of Apache, MySQL, PHP and Perl. It also comes with a number of other modules including OpenSSL, phpMyAdmin, MediaWiki, Joomla, Wordpress and more. Self-contained, multiple instances of XAMPP can exist on a single computer, and any given instance can be copied from one computer to

another. XAMPP is offered in both a full and a standard version (Smaller version).

2 MYSQL

MySQL and PHP have become the “bread and butter” of web application builders. It is the combination you are most likely to encounter today and probably for the years to come.

Strength:

Great Market Penetration

MySQL has the biggest market share of any open source database. Almost any web-hosting company can provide MySQL access, and books and articles about MySQL and PHP are abundant.

Easy to Get Started

After your database is set up and you have access to it, managing the database is straightforward. Initial access needs to be configured by a database administrator (if that person is not you). Tools such as MySQL Administrator or phpMyAdmin let you manage your database.

Open-Source License for Most Users

MySQL comes with a dual license—either GPL or a commercial license. You can use MySQL under the GPL as long as you are not commercially redistributing it.

Fast

MySQL has always been relatively fast, much due to its simplicity. In the last few years, MySQL has gained foothold in the enterprise market due to new “enterprise class” features and general maturity without compromising performance for simple usage.

Reasonable Scalability

MySQL used to be a lightweight database that did not have to drag around most of the expensive reliability features (such as transactions) of systems such as Oracle or IBM DB2. This was, and still is, one of the most important reasons for MySQL’s high performance. Today, MySQL has evolved to almost match its commercial seniors inscalability and reliability, but you can still configure it for lightweight use.

The most current stable version of MySQL is the 3.22.x, and you can obtain the latest revision from the main distribution site (<http://www.mysql.com/>) or from any of the many mirrors around the world. It is preferable that you use the mirror nearest to you.

Though the licensing of the MySQL database system is similar to open-source licenses, it is not exactly the same. You may have to pay for commercial usage. Older versions may be available under the GNU licensing, but since the licensing policy is evolving, it would be a better idea to consult the official homepage for exact

clarifications at a certain point in time. For Windows there is a special shareware version available.

There are several pre-compiled distributions of MySQL, if you do not feel comfortable compiling your own, or do not have access to a compiler in your system, one of these will be your best option. You may also prefer a binary distribution if you are not going to make big changes to the standard configuration, or add a particular module. Otherwise, for the maximum of flexibility, use the source code distribution.

6. SYSTEM DESIGN

6.1 System Design

Designing is the most important phase of software development. It requires a careful planning and thinking on the part of the system designer. Designing software means to plan how the various parts of the software are going to achieve the desired goal. It should be done with utmost care because if the phase contains any error then that will affect the performance of the system, as a result it may take more processing time, more response time, extra coding workload etc.

After the software requirements have been analyzed and specified, software design is the first of the three technical activities Designing, Coding and Testing that are required to build and verify the software. Each activity transforms information in such a manner that ultimately results in validated computer software.

Design goals

The following goals were kept in mind while designing the system:

- 1 **Make system user-friendly:** This was necessary so that system could be used efficiently and system could act as catalyst in achieving objectives.
- 2 **Make system compatible:** It should fit in the total integrated

system. Future maintenance and enhancement must be less.

3 **Make the system reliable:** understandable and cost-effective.

Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

It is a simple graphical formalism that can be used to represent a system in terms of the input data to the system, various processing carried out on these data and the output data generated by the system. The main reason why this DFD technique is so popular is probably because of the fact that DFD is a very simple formalism- it is simple to understand and use. A DFD model uses a very limited number of primitive symbols to represent the functions performed by a system and the data flow among these systems. Starting with a set of high-level functions that a system performance of DFD model in hierarchically it represent various sub functions. The Data Flow Diagramming technique also follows a simple set of intuitive concepts and rules.

Data flow diagram (DFD) is used to show how data flows through the system and the processes that transfer the input data into output. Data flow diagrams are a way of expressing system requirements in a graphical manner. DFD represents one of the most ingenious tools used for structured analysis.

In the normal convention, logical DFD can be completed using only four notations.

Function Symbol:

A function is represented using a circle. This symbol is called a process or a bubble. Bubbles are annotated with the names of corresponding functions.

External Entity Symbol:

An external entity such as a user, project manager etc. is represented by a rectangle. The external entities are essentially those physical entities external to the application system, which interact with the system by inputting data to the system or by consuming the data produced by the system. In addition to the human users the external entity symbols can be used to represent external hardware and software such as application software.

Data Flow Symbol:

A directed arc or an arrow is used as a Data Flow Symbol. This represents the data flow occurring between two processes or between an external entity and a process; in direction of the Data Flow Arrow. Data flow Symbols are annotated with corresponding data names.

Data Store Symbol:

A Data Store represents a logical file; it is represented using two parallel lines. A logical file can represent either Data Store Symbol, which can represent either data structure or a physical file on disk. Each data store is connected to a process by means of a Data Flow Symbol. The direction of the Data Flow Arrow shows whether data is being read from or written into a Data Store. An arrow flowing in or out of a data store implicitly represents the entire area of the Data Store and hence arrows connecting to a data store need not be annotated with the names of the corresponding data items.

Output Symbol:

The output symbol is used when a hardcopy is produced and the user of the copies cannot be clearly specified or there are several users of the output.

The DFD at the simplest level is referred to as the ‘CONTEXT ANALYSIS DIAGRAM’. These are expanded by level, each explaining its process in detail. Processes are numbered for easy identification and are normally labeled in block letters. Each data flow is labeled for easy understanding.

6.2 Data Flow Diagrams

0-Level DFD of Online Locker Management System

1-Level DFD

2-Level DFD

6.3. Database design

Online Locker Management System stores the data in a database. A database is a structured collection of data. To add, access, and process the data stored in database, one need a database management system such as MySQL server .MySQL is a relational database management system stores the data in separate tables .

The tables used in software project management system are,

- 1 Account table
- 2 Admin table
- 3 Locker table
- 4 User table

Account Table

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
Account_id	Int(10)	Primary key
Account_no.	Varchar(18)	Primary key
Address	Varchar(30)	Not null
D.O.B	Varchar(12)	Not null
F_name	Varchar(30)	Not null
Opening date	Varchar(12)	Not null
Signature	Varchar(30)	Primary Key

Admin table

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
Admin_id	Int(15)	Primary key
Email	Varchar(18)	Primary key
Name	Varchar(30)	Not null
Password	Varchar(12)	Not null

Locker Table

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
Created_on	Int(10)	Primary key
Descriptions	Varchar(18)	Not null
Locker_id	Varchar(30)	Not null
Locker_fee	Varchar(12)	Not null
Locker_name	Varchar(30)	Not null
Locker_number	int(12)	Primary Key
Locker_Status	Varchar(30)	Not null

User Table

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
Account_no.	Int(10)	Primary key
Created on	Varchar(18)	Not null
Address	Varchar(30)	Not null
D.O.B	Varchar(12)	Not null
F_name	Varchar(30)	Not null
Opening date	Varchar(12)	Not null
Signature	Varchar(30)	Primary Key
image	Varchar(25)	Primary key
ifsc	Varchar(26)	Not null
Password	Varchar(30)	Not null

6.4. Entity Relationship (ER) Diagram:-

The entity relationship data model is based on the perception of a real world that consists of a collection of basic objects called entities and the relationship among these objects. An entity is a thing or object in the real world that is differentiated from other objects.

An ER diagram can express the logical structure of a database graphically. The components of ER diagram are:-

1. : A rectangle represents entity set.
2. : A diamond represents the relationship among the entity set.
3. : An ellipse represents attributes.
4. : A line represents link to attributes to entity set and entity set to relationship.

6.5. Physical Design

Following the logical design is the physical design. This produces the working system by defining the design specifications that tell programmers exactly what the candidate system must do. In turn, the programmer writes necessary programs or modifies the software package that accepts input from the user. Two main stages in physical design are: input design and output design.

1 Input design(Form Design)

Input design is the process of converting user inputs into computer-based format. The project requires a set of information from the user to prepare a report. In order to prepare a report, when-organized input data are needed.

The goal behind designing input data is to make the data entry easy and make it free from logical errors. The input entry to all type of clients is the user name and password only. If they are valid the client is allowed to enter into the software.

Objectives

- To produce a cost-effective method of input.
- To achieve the highest possible level of accuracy.
- To ensure that the input is acceptable and understandable.

The input design is actually designing of screens. Some of the major screens involved in my project

- 1) Form for displaying result.

➤ **Output design**

Outputs are the most important and direct source of information to the user and to the management. Efficient and eligible output design should improve the system's relationship with the user and help in decision making. Output design generally deals with the results generated by the system that is reports. These reports can be generated from stored or calculated values.

Reports are displayed either as screen preview or printed form. Most end users will not actually operate the information systems or enter data through workstations, but they will use the output from the system.

Forms design

The cost of collecting raw data and cost of distributing processed information are major costs of a system. So careful forms

design can affect the cost effectiveness of the system. Well-designed forms can increase efficiency; improve workflow and lower system costs.

The major things that have been care of is that the forms must be easy to fill out in the case registration and easy to use.

Code design

When a large volume of data is being handled, it is important that items be identified, sorted or selected easily. To accomplish this, each data item must have a unique identification and must be relates to other items of data of the same type. Thus codes are used to identify item uniquely.

Code is a group of characters or numbers used to identify an item or data. While identification is the main function of a code, it may also show relationships between items of data. A good coding scheme should be expandable, precise, concise, convenient and meaningful. Based on the above idea, codes are used which contain alphanumeric characters.

SAMPLE CODE FOR ADMIN LOGIN

```
<!DOCTYPE
html>

  <html>
  <head>
  <meta charset="utf-8">
  <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
  <title>Admin Login</title>
```

```
<meta content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, maximum-scale=1,
user-scalable=no" name="viewport">
<link href="..system/files/css/bootstrap.min.css" rel="stylesheet">
<script src="..system/files/js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
<script src="..system/files/js/jquery.min.js"></script>

<style>
#header {
background: #ffffff none repeat scroll 0 0;
border-bottom: 1px solid #e5e5e5;
margin: 0;
min-height: 64px;
padding: 0;
}
.error_validate{
color:red; float:left;
margin-left: 37px;
margin-top: 4px; width:90%;
}
.form-group{
padding-bottom: 17px !important;
}
#footer {
height: 100px;
text-align: center;
}
</style>
</head>
<body>
<div id="container">
<header class="navbar navbar-static-top" id="header">
<div class="navbar-header">
<a class="navbar-brand" href="http://localhost:8080/locker"></a></div>
</header>
<div id="content">
<div class="container-fluid"><br>
```

```
<br>
<div class="row">
  <div class="col-sm-offset-4 col-sm-4">
    <div class="panel panel-default">
      <div class="panel-heading">
        <h1 class="panel-title"><i class="fa fa-lock"></i> Please enter your login
        details.</h1>
      </div>
      <div class="panel-body">

        <form method="POST" action="?key=auth">
          <div class="form-group">
            <label for="input-username">Login Id</label>
            <div class="input-group"><span class="input-group-addon"><span
            class="glyphicon glyphicon-envelope"></span></span></div>
            <input type="text" class="form-control" id="email" placeholder="Login Id"
            value="" name="email" required>
          </div>

          </div>
          <div class="form-group">
            <label for="input-password">Password</label>
            <div class="input-group"><span class="input-group-addon"><span
            class="glyphicon glyphicon-envelope"></span></span></div>
            <input type="password" class="form-control" id="input-password"
            placeholder="password" value="" name="password" required>
          </div>

          </div>
          <div class="text-right">
            <button class="btn btn-primary" type="submit" name="btn-login"
            value="Login"><i class="fa fa-key"></i>Login </button>
          </div>
        </form>

      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
```

```
</div>
</div>
<footer id="footer"><a href="">Panel</a> &copy; 2019 All Rights
Reserved.<br></footer></div>
</body>
</html>
```

OUTPUT OF THE ABOVE SOURCE CODE

Please enter your login details.

Login Id

Password

Login

Panel © 2019 All Rights Reserved.

SOURCE CODE OF DASHBOARD

```
<!DOCTYPE
html>
```

```
<html>
<head>
```

```
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
<title>Online Bank Locker </title>
<meta http-equiv="content-language" content="en" />
<meta content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, maximum-scale=1, user-
scalable=no" name="viewport">
<meta name="google" content="notranslate">
<link rel="stylesheet" href=" ../system/files/css/bootstrap.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="https://cdnjs.cloudflare.com/ajax/libs/font-
awesome/4.5.0/css/font-awesome.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href=" ../system/files/css/AdminLTE.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href=" ../system/files/css/ _all-skins.min.css">
<script type="text/javascript" src=" ../system/files/js/jquery.min.js"></script>
</head>
<body class="hold-transition skin-blue sidebar-mini">
<div class="wrapper">
<header class="main-header">
<nav class="navbar navbar-static-top">
<a href="#" class="sidebar-toggle" data-toggle="offcanvas" role="button">
<span class="sr-only">Toggle navigation</span>
</a>
<div class="navbar-custom-menu">
<ul class="nav navbar-nav">
<li class="dropdown user user-menu">
<a href="?key=my_profile" class="dropdown-toggle" data-
toggle="dropdown">
Profile
</a>
<ul class="dropdown-menu" style="width:302px !important;">
<li class="user-footer">
<div class="pull-left">
<a href="?key=change_password" class="btn btn-default btn-flat">Change
Password</a>
<!--a href="https://www.sualoo.com/Developer/admin/paypal" class="btn
```

```

btn-default btn-flat">Edit Paypal Id</a-->
<!--a href="#" class="btn btn-default btn-flat">Edit Paypal Id</a-->
</div>
<div class="pull-right">
<a href="?key=logout" class="btn btn-default btn-flat">Sign out</a>
</div>
</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
</nav>
</header>

<aside class="main-sidebar">
<section class="sidebar">
<ul class="sidebar-menu">
<li class="active treeview">
<a href="?key=Dashboard">
<i class="fa fa-dashboard"></i> <span>Dashboard</span>
</a>
</li>
<li class="treeview ">
<a href="?key=locker">
<i class="fa fa-bus"></i> <span>Lockers</span>
<i class="fa fa-angle-left pull-right"></i>
</a>
<ul class="treeview-menu">
<li><a href="?key=add_locker"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i> Add
Locker</a></li>
<li><a href="?key=view_locker"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i> Show
Locker</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
<li class="treeview ">
<a href="#">

```

```
<i class="fa fa-user"></i> <span>User Account</span>
<i class="fa fa-angle-left pull-right"></i>
</a>
<ul class="treeview-menu">
<li><a href="?key=active_account"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i>Active
Account</a></li>
<li><a href="?key=inactive_account"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i>In-active
Account</a></li>
<li><a href="?key=create_account"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i>Create
Account</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
<li class="treeview ">
<a href="#">
<i class="fa fa-user"></i> <span>External Users</span>
<i class="fa fa-angle-left pull-right"></i>
</a>
<ul class="treeview-menu">
<li><a href="?key=active_user"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i>Approved
Users</a></li>
<li><a href="?key=inactive_user"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i>Rejected
Users</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
<li class="treeview ">
<a href="#">
<i class="fa fa-user"></i> <span>Locker Booking</span>
<i class="fa fa-angle-left pull-right"></i>
</a>
<ul class="treeview-menu">
<li><a href="?key=active_user"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i>Approved
request</a></li>
<li><a href="?key=inactive_user"><i class="fa fa-circle-o"></i>Rejected
request</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
```

```
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</section>
</aside>
<div class="content-wrapper">
<section class="content-header">
<h1>
<a href="https://www.sualoo.com/Developer/admin"><i class="fa fa-
dashboard"> </i> Home</a>
<small>Dashboard</small>
</h1>
</section>
<!-- Main content -->
<section class="content">
<div class="row">
<div class="col-lg-3 col-xs-6">
<div class="small-box bg-olive">
<div class="inner">
<h3>Total Account <br> <strong>1</strong></h3>
</div>
<div class="icon">
<i class="ion ion-bag"></i>
</div>
<a href="https://www.sualoo.com/Developer/admin/banner/manage"
class="small-box-footer">More info <i class="fa fa-arrow-circle-
right"></i></a>
</div>
</div>
<div class="col-lg-3 col-xs-6">
<div class="small-box bg-aqua">
<div class="inner">
<h3>Total Locker <br> <strong>2</strong> </h3>
</div>
<div class="icon">
```

```
<i class="ion ion-bag"></i>
</div>
<a href="https://www.sualoo.com/Developer/admin/page/manage"
class="small-box-footer">More info <i class="fa fa-arrow-circle-
right"></i></a>
</div>
</div>
<div class="col-lg-3 col-xs-6">
<div class="small-box bg-purple">
<div class="inner">
<h3>Booked Locker <br> <strong>0</strong> </h3>
</div>
<div class="icon">
<i class="ion ion-bag"></i>
</div>
<a href="https://www.sualoo.com/Developer/admin/approved_driver"
class="small-box-footer">More info <i class="fa fa-arrow-circle-
right"></i></a>
</div>
</div>
<div class="col-lg-3 col-xs-6">
<div class="small-box bg-lime">
<div class="inner">
<h3>Available Locker <br> <strong>2</strong></h3>
</div>
<div class="icon">
<i class="ion ion-bag"></i>
</div>
<a href="https://www.sualoo.com/Developer/admin/testimonial/manage"
class="small-box-footer">More info <i class="fa fa-arrow-circle-
right"></i></a>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</section>
</div>
<footer class="main-footer">
```

```
<div class="pull-right hidden-xs">
<b>Version</b> 2.3.3
</div>
<strong>Copyright &copy; 2014-2015 <a href="#">Almsaeed
Studio</a>.</strong> All rights
reserved.
</footer>

<div class="control-sidebar-bg"></div>
</div>

<script src=" ../system/files/js/jquery.js"></script>
<script src=" ../system/files/js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>

<script type="text/javascript">
</script>

<script src=" ../system/files/js/app.min.js"></script>
```

OUTPUT OF THE ABOVE SOURCE CODE

7. SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

System development is a series of operations performed to manipulate data to produce output from a computer system. This is highly dependent on the programming language used. During the system development phase, the system is constructed from the specifications prepared in the design phase. The principal activities performed during the development phase can be divided into two major related sequences. They are:

- 1 External system development
- 2 Internal system development

The major external system development activities are:

- 1 Implementation
- 2 Planning
- 3 Equipment acquisition
- 4 Installation

The major internal system development activities are:

- 1 Computer program development
- 2 Performance testing
 - (i)Xampp Control Panel
 - (ii)check from Phpmyadmin

7.1. Code Design

The purpose of the code is to facilitate the identification and the retrieval of items of information. A code is an ordered collection of

symbols designed to provide unique identification of an entity or an attribute. Codes are built with mutually exclusive features. Code in all cases specify object's

physical or on performance characteristics. They are used to give operational distractions and other information.

Codes also show interrelationship among different items. Codes are used for identifying, accessing, sorting and matching records. The code ensures that only one value of code with a single meaning is correctly applied to give entity or attribute as described in various ways.

8. SYSTEM TESTING AND IMPLEMENTATION

8.1 Testing

Software testing is a critical element of software quality assurance and represents the ultimate review of specification, design and coding. Testing presents an interesting anomaly for the software. The testing phase for the ‘Software project monitoring system’ involves testing of this system using various test data.

System testing

The various testing methods that has been approached for the testing of software project management system are

- 1 Unit testing
- 2 Integration testing
- 3 Validation testing

Unit testing

In computer programming, unit testing is a software verification and validation method in which a programmer tests if individual units of source code are fit for use. A unit is the smallest testable part of an application. In procedural programming a unit may be an individual program, function, procedure, etc., while in object-oriented programming, the smallest unit is a class, which may belong to a base/super class, abstract class or derived/child class. In this project there are two units:

1. User’s part
2. Admin’s part

Conditional testing

In this part of testing each and every condition in the Customer Care and Billing System for GSM Network is tested to both true and false aspects and all resulting paths were tested.

Loop testing

In this type of testing all the loops involved in the Customer Care and Billing System for GSM Network are tested to all the limits possible.

Integration testing

Integration testing is systematic technique for constructing the program structure. As an integrated testing approach different part of software are combined. The top-down strategy has been used for upper level and bottom-up level approach is used for subordinate levels

Validation testing

Validation testing succeeds when software functions in a manner that is expected. Some of the validations imposed in my project are as follows

- 1 Forms cannot be submitted without filling up the mandatory data so that Manuel mistakes of submitting fields that are empty can be sorted out.
- 2 All date enters are validated as per system requirement
- 3 Forms cannot be submitted without writing emailid in the correct

- format so that manual mistakes like these can be avoided.
- 4 User is provided with appropriate error messages about the operation errors.
 - 5 Access permissions to various type of user are controlled according to the organizational structure.

Consistency testing

All functions, informations, help messages are tested to make consistent the system ensures uniform look and feel thought the application .

Portability testing

The system is tested under different operating systems to ensure platform independed.no failures occurred.

User environment testing

Staff members of this company have worked as the end users of the system. no failures has occurred.

White-Box Test(Glass Test)

White-Box testing can be called as functional testing. This deals with the testing of logic and control. This is completely related with the working of program body. Here the program is considered first and output is considered next. By keeping the output in mind tests each control block and logical unit. Special care has been taken to eradicate the abnormality in all levels.

White-Box testing of software is predicted on close examination of procedural details. Logical paths through the software are tested by providing test cases that exercises specific set of conditions or loops.

Black-Box Testing

Internal Functionality of the software is hidden.

User Acceptance Testing

User acceptance testing of a system is the key factor for the success of any system. The system under consideration is tested for user acceptance by constantly keeping in touch with prospective system users at time of developing and making changes whenever required. The system considered is tested for user acceptance; here it should satisfy the firm's need too. This done with regard to Input screen Design; output Screen Design, Online message to guide user and the like.

8.2. Implementation

Implementation is the process of bringing a newly developed system or revised into operational one. It is the practical job of putting a theoretical design into practice. It may involve the complete implementation of a computer complex or the introduction of one small subsystem. The new system and its components are to be tested in a

structured and planned manner. The implementation stage of a project is often very complex and time consuming and many more people are involved in the earlier stages.

Software project monitoring system is implemented as a complete web application. a web application is an application running on a server that a user accesses through a thin general purpose client. The client is a web browser.

The implementation phase of a project covers the period from the acceptance of the tested design to its satisfactory operations, supported by the appropriate user and operations manual. It is a major operation across the whole organizational structure and requires a great deal of planning. The implementation plan involves the following:

- 1 Testing to confirm effectiveness
- 2 Detection and correction of errors
- 3 Making necessary changes so as to satisfy the requirements

9. SYSTEM MAINTENANCE

Software Development has many phases. These phases include Requirements Engineering, Architecting, Design, Implementation, Testing, Software Deployment, and Maintenance. Maintenance is the last stage of the software life cycle. After the product has been released, the maintenance phase keeps the software up to date with environment changes and changing user requirements. The earlier phases should be done so that the product is easily maintainable. The design phase should plan the structure in a way that can be easily altered. Similarly, the Software maintenance is the modification of a software product after delivery to correct faults, to improve performance or other attributes, or to adapt the product to a modified environment implementation phase should create code that can be easily read, understood, and changed. Maintenance can only happen efficiently if the earlier phases are done properly.

There are four major problems that can slow down the maintenance process: unstructured code, maintenance programmers having insufficient knowledge of the system, documentation being absent, out of date, or at best insufficient, and software maintenance having a bad image. The success of the maintenance phase relies on these problems

being fixed earlier in the life cycle.

Maintenance consists of four parts. Corrective maintenance deals with fixing bugs in the code. Adaptive maintenance deals with adapting the software to new environments. Perfective maintenance deals with updating the software according to changes in user requirements. Finally, preventive maintenance deals with updating documentation and making the software more maintainable. All changes to the system can be characterized by these four types of maintenance. Corrective maintenance is ‘traditional maintenance’ while the other types are considered as ‘software evolution.’

10. FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The application developed is designed in such a way that any further enhancements can be done with ease. New modules can be added to the existing system with less effort. The future enhancement in software project monitoring system can be done by adding

1. Chatting and video conference for communications.
2. Using group message service for informing registered user for any changes.

This module are kept as future enhancement for implementation

New modules can be added to the existing system with less effort .The software can be given a new looking and new features can be added thereby improving the efficiency of the entire system.

11. CONCLUSION

This web application provides facility to conduct online locker management worldwide. It saves time as it allows number of customers to apply for locker at a time and displays the result as the locker requests applied over, so need to wait for the result. It is automatically generated by the server.

Administrator has a privilege to create , modify and delete the locker details and it's particular customer. User can register, login and apply for the bank locker with his/her specific id and can see the result as well.

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